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TEACHING THE ENGLISH SEGMENTAL PHONEMES THRU TECHNOLOGY-MEDIATED AND FACE-TO-FACE MODES

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Abstract

This study aimed at determining the effect of Technology-Mediated (T-M) and Face-to-Face (F-t-F) as methods of teaching the English segmental phonemes to students in the tertiary level. This study adopted the quasi-experimental pretest-posttest design and employed two treatment groups comprising T-M instruction class and F-t-F instruction class. The Mann-Whitney U test revealed that there is no significant difference in the means of the pretest scores of students' oral production of English segmental phonemes exposed to T-M and F-t-F instructional methods. This indicates that the students in the T-M and F-t-F instructional classes did not differ significantly in their pretest performance. Both classes had more or less the same ability at the start of the treatment period and, therefore, comparable in terms of their pretest proficiency. However, there is a significant difference in the means of the posttest scores of the students' oral production of English segmental phonemes when exposed to T-M and F-t-F instructional methods. This shows that although both classes obtained "satisfactory" posttest performance from "moderately satisfactory," the F-t-F class performed better than the T-M class. The result apparently reveals that the real live teacher can still be considered more effective in the delivery instruction such as teaching the English segmental phonemes. The investigation further aimed at determining whether or not there is a significant difference in the means of the pretest and posttest proficiency of students' oral production of English segmental phonemes exposed to T-M and F-t-F. The Wilcoxon Signed Ranks test revealed that there is a positive and significant difference in the means of the pretest and posttest proficiency of students' oral production of English segmental phonemes exposed to T-M and F-t-F instructional methods. Therefore, the T-M and F-t-F instructional methods in teaching the English segmental phonemes were both effective for the students' proficiency in their oral production of the English segmental phonemes.

Keywords: Technology-mediated, face-to-face teaching, pronunciation, teaching strategies, English segmental phonemes, teaching modes

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